

IOT BASED FARM PROTECTION FROM ANIMALS AND HUMAN THEFT USING ESP32 WITH CAMERA MODULE

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ABSTRACT

Manual irrigation is still widely used in agricultural field using traditional drip and can watering. However, traditional irrigation systems are inefficient and inexact, leading to either insufficient or excessive watering. Moreover, it is difficult for farmers to predict suitable quantities at the appropriate time. Manual monitoring of the crop field may also lead to human error and is potentially risky for rural areas. Farmers may also not be aware of intrusions if they are not on location. Therefore, this project is designed to develop a smart monitoring and automated irrigation system to provide not only efficient water consumption based on specific conditions, but also enables real-time monitoring of the environment. Furthermore, this system prevents damage to plants and reduces the likelihood of plant theft. This system uses NodeMCU ESP32 as a microcontroller that collects environmental data such as humidity, temperature, soil moisture levels from sensors. The NodeMCU is integrated with a relay and RTC module to irrigate plants at specific times and is also equipped with a passive infrared sensor to detect intruders near the crop-field. Upon detection, an ESP32 camera is used to automatically capture the current conditions and farmers will be subsequently notified. Warnings are also sent to farmers upon detection of unwanted circumstances such as extreme temperature, which could prevent instances of open burning. The utility of the developed prototype is evident in the way it automatically irrigates the crop field without human intervention. Farmers may monitor and manually control the irrigation process using an attached Android application. Additionally, they may manually activate a buzzer warn off any potential malicious actors.

I. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture leads the world's water consumption, with farming and food production accounting up to 70% and is also one of the major sectors that contributes to the economic growth. Apart from its importance in providing raw materials and major source of food, agriculture has also contributed to 8.2% of national gross income in 2017, which is a vital part of a country's income. With so much water consumption used in this sector, one would expect an over-abundance of water resources dedicated to agriculture. However, one of the largest contributors to water wastage is no doubt caused by low irrigation efficiency. This is seen in many irrigation systems which still relies on traditional and widely used methods such as using watering cans as shown in Figure 1. However, an important limitation is that farmers have difficulties in monitoring and irrigating crop fields in remote locations. Inefficient use of water leads to excessive water consumption dedicated to plants. Moreover, farmers sometimes cannot predict a suitable level of water consumption, which affects the quality of the plants (too much or too little) and may lead to the water wastage. Furthermore, manual monitoring of the crop-field may lead to human error, and is also risky and potentially dangerous for certain types of rural areas, such as those bordering on wildlife areas.

This project is developed with the help of latest technology of Internet of Things (IoT) which can provide real-time measurement of temperatures and soil moisture levels using several on-site sensors. The developed system can also remotely monitor the irrigation system via the Internet. IoT is an emerging technology that is currently penetrating other automation systems such as smart home, smart farming, smart factory, and wearable smart bands. IoT technology can offer efficient way of implementing automatic irrigation system.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Research on developing a smart agriculture system have attracted significant amount of attention from researchers over the years. The following subsections discuss several smart agriculture and intrusion detection available in the markets. 2.1 Smart Crop Monitoring System Several related works have been found in

literature. Ashifuddinmondal and Rehena [3] developed a system to monitor plants and control the water supply through a smartphone. The system integrates various sensors to measure the water content of soil and detect the temperature using soil moisture and temperature sensors respectively. This project makes use of Raspberry Pi to connect between the sensors and cloud server, and users can connect their smartphone to the raspberry pi using Bluetooth Module. A faster approach has been proposed by the authors in using Wi-Fi to send sensors data to the cloud using Arduino. This can also connect to multiple devices at once. Next, an improvement has been done by Jindarat and Wuttidittachotti which has introduced a system that can track ambient of weather conditions including humidity, temperature, atmosphere performance and fan power control in chicken farm. Using this design, farmers can easily monitor and control their farm condition using their smartphone. A similar approach has been proposed in . Further enhancement has been done in this design which includes farm monitoring using smartphone and web application. This significantly makes the system easier to be used and can monitor farms from multiple devices. Further improvement can be seen in using Web Camera to monitor remote location of crop field by capturing time lapse images of the plant efficiently. A similar approach is also implemented in [8] with more secure design. The system used an IoT platform such as System Under Analysis based on Agro-Meteorology system for Viticulture Disease Warning. This system is used to monitor the vineyard using secure wireless or actuator sensor while server sub-system is used to transmit data to server. An enhanced method is proposed by authors in . Two software are used to produce recommendation for solution needed by farmer which are PHP programming language and MATLAB to manage and synchronize IoT sensor for easy reading according to specific sensor range. 2.2 Automated Irrigation System The article in describes a system that is developed to manage water flow and power management for an irrigation system. In this design, the optimal water supply was calculated using the approximate information of an ambiguous expert method. A similar technique has been proposed by the authors . This later system assessed an event-based irrigation system by utilizing tomato plants. This method is used to reduce water consumption to improve the efficiency of the system. Apart from that, a system proposed by authors in make use of renewable source such as solar power to implement automatic irrigation system. The main goal of this method is to develop a low cost and time-based irrigation system. A similar approach to irrigation system has been proposed by.

III. EXISTING SYSTEM

To automate the agriculture land and protect the land and crops using IOT This system automates the agriculture land by supplying the water to the crops on the basis of temperature and their requirement. It also monitors the removal of excess water accumulated in the field The protection is provided to the land using IOT, Sensors are used to detect any animals and birds entering the land and they are avoided[8]

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

1. In this project we are measuring the water level content in the crop by using a water level sensor and also, we are measuring soil moisture content in the crop by using a soil moisture sensor.
2. For Protecting the crop from animals and humans, we are keeping ESP32 cam module. By using this module, if an intruder is detected, then it captures the image and sends a message through the telegram app.
3. We are using an automatic flashlight to capture the images for protecting the crop during the night times. 4. Here we use a buzzer to alert us whenever there is some harm to the crop.
5. We are also analyzing crop growth by taking pictures of the crop at specified time intervals [9].

V. METHODOLOGY

The efficiency of the proposed module is to develop an effective system for practicing agriculture and growing food in a sustainable way. The system with the additions made, makes use of the wireless sensor networks which cumulates data from contrasting sensors deployed at various nodes and sends it through the wireless protocol. The add-ons consist of temperature and humidity sensor[10] (DHT11), moisture sensor (YL-69), water level sensor and DC motor. When the agriculture monitoring system based on Internet of Things starts, it checks the water level, humidity and moisture level, alongside detecting the presence of any living beings around the farm. It sends alert on the phone about the levels. Sensors sense the level of water if it goes down, it automatically starts the water pump. If the temperature goes above the level, fan starts. This all is displayed on

the LCD(16×2) display module[11]. The data may also be stored in the Blynk App, open platform cloud based service, which would aid the operator in data visualization. If given the provision, the proposed module may be incorporated with high-tech laser, which may scare away the animal, which if by any means tries to invade the farms and destroy the crops.

VI. HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

IR sensor:

An infrared (IR) sensor[12] is an electronic device that measures and detects infrared radiation in its surrounding environment. Infrared radiation was accidentally discovered by an astronomer named William Herchel in 1800. While measuring the temperature of each color of light (separated by a prism), he noticed that the temperature just beyond the red light was highest. IR is invisible to the human eye, as its wavelength is longer than that of visible light (though it is still on the same electromagnetic spectrum). Anything that emits heat (everything that has a temperature above around five degrees Kelvin) gives off infrared radiation[13].

LCD:

Depending on how many lines are used for connection to the microcontroller, there are 8-bit and 4-bit LCD modes. The appropriate mode is determined at the beginning of the process in a phase called “initialization”. In the first case, the data are transferred through outputs D0-D7 as it has been already explained. In case of 4-bit LED mode, for the sake of saving valuable I/O pins of the microcontroller, there are only 4 higher bits (D4-D7) used for communication, while other may be left unconnected[14].

Consequently, each data is sent to LCD in two steps: four higher bits are sent first (that normally would be sent through lines D4-D7), four lower bits are sent afterwards. With the help of initialization, LCD will correctly connect and interpret each data received. Besides, with regards to the fact that data are rarely read from LCD (data mainly are transferred from microcontroller to LCD) one more I/O pin may be saved by simple connecting R/W pin to the Ground. Such saving has its price. Even though message displaying will be normally performed, it will not be possible to read from busy flag since it is not possible to read from display.

Capacitive soil moisture sensor:

This soil moisture sensor measures soil moisture levels by capacitive sensing rather than resistive sensing like other sensors on the market. It is made of corrosion-resistant material which gives it excellent service life. Insert it into the soil around your plants and monitor the real-time soil moisture data.

Water level sensor:

This sensor works by having a series of exposed traces connected to ground and interlaced between the grounded traces are the sens traces. The sensor traces have a weak pull-up resistor of 1 MΩ. The resistor will pull the sensor trace value high until a drop of water shorts the sensor trace to the grounded trace.

ESP32 camera:

The ESP32-CAM is a small size, low power consumption camera module based on ESP32. It comes with an OV2640 camera and provides onboard TF card slot. The ESP32-CAM can be widely used in intelligent IoT applications such as wireless video monitoring, WiFi image upload, QR identification, and so on.

VII. RESULT

VIII. CONCLUSION

The IOT based farm monitoring and protection system using ESP32 with camera module acts as bot for alerting the farm owner whenever intruder is detected. This system identifies movement of living beings and captures the image. This works on microcontroller and camera module. Arduino IDE is used to write and dump the code

to the microcontroller board. Blynk application is used to send alert messages and images to the farm owner. By using these devices and technologies we have developed a system to detect and inform about wild animals to the farm owner which reduces the crop damage by animals and helps farmers in getting better yields. We have also developed a monitoring system in that we have measured the moisture content in the soil and water level . which will gives the high production rates.

IX. REFERENCES

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